

Scalable Quantum Approximate Optimiser for Pseudo-Boolean Multi-Objective Optimisation

Zakaria Abdelmoiz Dahi¹[0000-0001-8022-4407], Francisco Chicano²[0000-0003-1259-2990], Gabriel Luque²[0000-0001-7909-1416], Bilel Derbel¹[0000-0002-4156-8490], and Enrique Alba²[0000-0002-5520-8875]

¹ Univ. Lille, Inria, CNRS, Centrale Lille, UMR 9189 CRISTAL, F-59000 Lille, France

² ITIS Software, University of Malaga, Malaga, Spain

{abdelmoiz-zakaria.dahi, bilel.derbel}@inria.fr
{chicano, gluque, eat}@uma.es

Abstract. Quantum computation uses quantum mechanical principles to reach beyond-classical computational power. This has endless applications, especially in optimisation-problems' solving. Most of today's quantum optimisers, more specifically, Quantum Approximate Optimisation Algorithm (QAOA), were originally designed to solve single-objective problems, although real-life scenarios include generally dealing with multiple objectives. Very preliminary literature with design/implementation limitations has been done in this sense. This makes dealing with such limitations and expanding the QAOA applicability to multi-objective optimisation an important step towards advancing quantum computation. To do so, this work presents a decomposition-based Multi-Objective QAOA (MO-QAOA) able to solve multi-objective problems. The proposal's design explores QAOA's features considering the error-prone and limited nature of today's quantum computers as well as the costly quantum simulation. This work's contributions stand in designing both, (I) sequential and parallel MO-QAOA, based on (II) weighted-sum and Tchebycheff scalarisation, by (III) exploring the QAOA's parameters' transference. The validation has been done using 2, 3 and 4-objectives problems of several sizes/complexities/types, using up to 2000 slaves/jobs running quantum computer simulators, as well as three real IBM 127-qubits' quantum computers. The results show up to 89% execution-time decrease, which supports the applicability/reliability of the proposal in today's time-constrained and error-prone quantum computers.

Keywords: Quantum Computing · Multi-objective Optimisation.

1 Introduction

Quantum Computation (QC), based on the principles of quantum physics (e.g. superposition, entanglement, etc.), is able to provide a computational speed-up over classical computing [12]. This has numerous applications, especially in optimisation-problem solving [2]. Regarding the former, two QC paradigms exist: quantum annealing and gate-based quantum computing. This work investigates optimisers designed for discrete gate-based quantum computers, considering its wider applicability, investigation and support by manufacturers. Although quantum technology is gaining more interest, it is still in a Noisy Intermediate Scale

Quantum era (NISQ), with limited qubits' number and noise robustness. So, this work investigates a relatively-recent quantum solver; the Quantum Approximate Optimisation Algorithm (QAOA) [10] knowing that it can still provide promising performances regardless of the NISQ nature of the quantum technology, and can, theoretically, guarantee solving-optimality under certain conditions.

QAOA was devised originally to solve single-objective problems, where its performances have been actively investigated. This being said, most real-life problems usually imply considering several conflicting objectives [1]. To this end, rethinking QAOA to be also applicable on such type of problems is crucial towards exploring the advantages of such algorithms, or even quantum computation, in real-world applications. To the best of the authors' knowledge, only three works have investigated Variational Quantum Algorithms (VQAs) in a multi-objective context [3,8,9], including only one researching specifically the QAOA [3]. All the aforementioned works present some design or implementation shortfalls which might be a handicap towards their applicability and efficiency. Considering specifically the work in [3] addressing the QAOA, from a design point of view: (I) the decomposition's design might be an issue, (II) it does not explore some interesting features of the QAOA such as parameters' distribution concentration and transference that might lead to a more efficient design [14]. Now, from an implementation aspect, the proposal does not consider two very important facts: (I) quantum computers are in their NISQ era with quite delaying queuing systems, and (II) quantum simulation requirements increase exponentially with respect to the problems' size.

This work proposes both *sequential* and *parallel* approaches to research the limitations in [3], where the *sequential* proposal investigates the design shortfalls by exploring a weighted-sum scalarisation and, for the first time in the literature, Tchebycheff decomposition as well as the QAOA's parameters' concentration/transference. The *parallel* approach deals with the implementation issues by leveraging the parallel use of quantum computers/simulators. The validation has been done on large and diverse benchmarks (2-4 min-max objectives, 4-127 variables), using the largest IBM real gate-based quantum computers (127 qubits) and quantum simulators (up to 2000). It is worth stating that our claims are with regard to the VQAs' literature in Multi-Objective Optimisation (MOO). One should note that this work's purpose is not proving quantum advantage neither outperforming the state-of-the-art classical solvers, as this would be hardly achievable considering today's small-scale/NISQ nature of quantum machines. Instead, we aim to (I) prepare the foundations to do so when scalable/stable quantum hardware will be available, and (II) explore the strength/weaknesses of nowadays' quantum optimisers/computers regarding classical ones.

The rest of the paper presents some background on quantum computing, QAOA, and MOO in Section 2. Afterwards, Section 3 thoroughly analyses the literature. In Section 4, the proposed approach is introduced, while Section 5 assesses its efficiency. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 Preliminary Concepts

This section presents fundamentals of QC, QAOA and MOO.

2.1 Quantum Computing and Approximate Optimisation

Quantum computing in a discrete gate-based model describes computation as quantum circuits. The former consists in a set of quantum gates acting on quantum bits (or qubits) [12]. Unlike classical bits, which can take either value 0 or 1, the qubits can be in a superposition of both states. Formally, the quantum state $|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$ of a qubit is the superposition of both basis state $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, having α and β as probability amplitudes. Based on the Born rule, the probability of measuring 0 and 1 is $\mathcal{P}_z(\langle 0|\psi\rangle) = |\alpha|^2$ and $\mathcal{P}_z(\langle 1|\psi\rangle) = |\beta|^2$, respectively, where $\mathcal{P}_z(\langle 1|\psi\rangle) + \mathcal{P}_z(\langle 0|\psi\rangle) = 1$. Considering the quantum gates, they are unitary operators \mathcal{U} , with the property $\mathcal{U}\mathcal{U}^\dagger = \mathcal{U}^\dagger\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{I}$, where \mathcal{U}^\dagger is the adjoint of \mathcal{U} (conjugate transpose) and \mathcal{I} is the identity matrix. The state of $|\psi\rangle$ evolves in a complex Hilbert space \mathcal{H} and the quantum state of n qubits $|\psi_*\rangle$ lives in the tensor product of n complex Hilbert spaces $\mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}$.

Fig. 1. Execution workflow of the QAOA

QAOA is a hybrid quantum algorithm represented by a layered application of unitary transformations called *ansatz*. Concretely, the QAOA's building blocks are the problem unitary and the mixer unitary. The first one is a unitary transformation that depends on the problem Hamiltonian \mathcal{H}_P , while the second depends on a mixer Hamiltonian \mathcal{H}_M . QAOA stands in two components: a quantum and a classical one. The quantum component is an ansatz that produces a state $|\psi_{(\gamma,\beta)}\rangle$ after applying p pairs of the problem unitary and the mixer unitary applied to n qubits prepared in a superposition state using the Walsh-Hadamard transform $\mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}$ (see Eq. (1)). The i^{th} pair of layers ($\mathcal{H}_P, \mathcal{H}_M$) is parameterised with two parameters γ_i and β_i , where p layers use $2p$ parameters. The classical component optimises the sets of parameters $\gamma = \{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_p\}$ and $\beta = \{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_p\}$ to minimise the expectation value $\mathcal{F}_{(\gamma,\beta)}$ defined in Eq. (2).

$$\mathcal{U}_{(\gamma,\beta)} = \bigotimes_{j=1}^p (e^{-i\beta_j \mathcal{H}_M} e^{-i\gamma_j \mathcal{H}_P}) \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n} = \bigotimes_{j=1}^p \left(e^{-i\beta_j \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{X}_i} e^{-i\gamma_j \mathcal{H}_P} \right) \mathcal{H}^{\otimes n}, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{(\gamma,\beta)} = \langle \psi_{(\gamma,\beta)} | \mathcal{H}_P | \psi_{(\gamma,\beta)} \rangle. \quad (2)$$

2.2 Multi-objective and Pseudo-Boolean Optimisation

Solving a multi-objective problem \mathcal{F}_* stands in solving simultaneously a set of \mathcal{K} min/max optimisation problems $\{\mathcal{F}_1, \dots, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{K}}\}$, where $\mathcal{F}_i : x \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, \dots, \mathcal{K}$, and $\mathcal{F}_* : x \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{K}}$. A solution x_1 is said to weakly dominate another one x_2 , denoted $x_1 \preceq x_2$, when $\mathcal{F}_i(x_1) \leq \mathcal{F}_i(x_2)$, for $i = 1, \dots, \mathcal{K}$. Also, x_1 is said to dominate x_2 , denoted as $x_1 \prec x_2$, when $x_1 \preceq x_2$ and $\exists i \in \{1, \dots, \mathcal{K}\}$ where $\mathcal{F}_i(x_1) < \mathcal{F}_i(x_2)$. Finally, x_1 is said to strictly dominate x_2 , and denoted $x_1 \ll x_2$, when $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, \mathcal{K}\}$, $\mathcal{F}_i(x_1) < \mathcal{F}_i(x_2)$ [1]. It is worth noting that normal and strict dominance are more likely to be considered in this work.

Optimisation problems to be solved in MOO can be of different types, although in this present work, a special interest is given to pseudo-Boolean problems. In general, an n -dimensional pseudo-Boolean problem can be defined as

$$\mathcal{F}(x) = \sum_{\mathcal{S} \subseteq [n]} \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{S}} \prod_{j \in \mathcal{S}} x_j, \quad (3)$$

where we define $[n] = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, \mathcal{S} is a subset of variables from $[n]$, $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{S}}$ is the coefficient of the term involving the product of variables in \mathcal{S} and $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$ is a binary string $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$. In this work, we focus on quadratic and higher-order problems where $2 \leq |\mathcal{S}|$. Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimisation (QUBO) can be defined using Eq. (4), where x is an n -dimensional column vector, x^T its transpose, and \mathcal{Q} is an $n \times n$ interaction matrix [11].

$$\mathcal{F}(x) = x^T \mathcal{Q} x \quad (4)$$

3 Review of Quantum Multi-Objective Optimisation

To the best of our knowledge, three works have studied VQAs in the context of MOO [3,8,9], including only one that focused on QAOA. Each of the approaches had shortfalls in some aspects. First, in [8] a Variational Quantum Eigen Solver (VQE) is used to tackle constrained problems as bi-objective problems, where the problem is the first objective and its constraints are the second one. During optimisation, a non-dominated front is generated, although only solution(s) that satisfy all the constraints and minimise the best energy function are picked. This approach does not guarantee the multi-objective nature (i.e. conflicting) between both objectives. Besides, the multi-objectivity is handled in the algorithm's classical part where NSGA-II [6] optimises the VQE ansatz parameters. Actually, it is not clear which Hamiltonian is being optimised, although as described, the VQE does not handle the MOO problem using its quantum routine.

The authors in [9] devise a VQA that solves a combination of the multi/many-objectives (up to 5) unconstrained minimisation problems. The VQA's parameters optimisation is done with regard to the hypervolume indicator [1] using non-gradient-based methods, COBYLA and FGBSC. Doing so poses some shortcomings regarding other metrics such as the Inverted Generational Distance and its variant (IGD and IGD⁺) (i.e. the high computational cost, nadir point selection, etc.) [1]. The unitary transformation describing the algorithm is composed

of \mathcal{L} layers. Each layer is composed of \mathcal{K} blocks. Each block combines the mixer and phase unitaries representing one of the \mathcal{K} problems to be solved. The \mathcal{N} most sampled solutions are considered as a non-dominated set. Such design leads to high-depth ansatz, which might make the computation unfeasible knowing the NISQ nature of today’s quantum machines. Also, having \mathcal{K} problems will involve optimising $2\mathcal{L}\mathcal{K}$ parameters which hardens the optimisation process compared to a vanilla VQA of \mathcal{K} factor less parameters. In addition, the proposed approach is based on qudits which is more computationally expensive to simulate, unstable and not widely available. Actually, the authors mention the use of qudits, but do not indicate which quantum system/simulator has been used. If any simulation was done, simulating the quantum state of \mathcal{N} qudits will require $d^{\mathcal{N}}$ memory.

The work in [3] proposes a QAOA-based approach to tackle the multi-objective formulation of some small instances of the network routing problem. The proposal solves the weighted aggregation of up-to 4 conflicting QUBOs. This being said, weighted-sum scalarisation might have some shortfalls compared to other scalarisation techniques such as Tchebycheff that finds solutions in non-convex parts of the Pareto front [4]. The authors consider the weighted sum of quadratic polynomials expressed by both the problems and their constraints (as penalty functions). Using the weighted sum to solve problems of this type would require giving a different weight to each QUBO representing both the problem and penalties together. However, the authors dissociated the problems and penalties by assigning them different weights, which impacts differently the penalisation of feasible/unfeasible solutions. Similarly to [9], the authors solve the Hamiltonian representing the weighted sum of objectives and penalties, then extracts a set of non-dominated fronts during sampling. Alternatively, they solve the weighted sum using different weight aggregations, where a non-dominated front is extracted when solving each Hamiltonian. The final front is extracted from the union of all the non-dominated fronts using a non-dominated sorting routine that is quadratic in terms of the number of sampled solutions \mathcal{N} and objectives \mathcal{M} ($\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}^2)$ [6]). Such complexity increases to $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{Z}\mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}^2)$ when having \mathcal{Z} aggregation-weights’ combinations. The first approach was mainly researched, while the second has been explored with just 3 weight combinations.

4 The Proposed Approach

The proposed sequential approach investigates the design issues in [3,8,9], while its parallelisation researches the implementation limitations. In the following, we will start describing first the sequential approach, then move to the parallel one.

Algorithm 1 The Proposed Sequential/Parallel MO-QAOA

Require: \mathcal{Z} aggregation-weight configurations

<pre> 1: for $i = 1 \dots \mathcal{Z}$ do 2: Solve \mathcal{F}_* using i^{th} weight configuration 3: Extract the i^{th} non-dominated front \mathcal{S}'_i 4: Set γ and β values as seed for solving the $(i + 1)^{th}$ instance of \mathcal{F}_* 5: $\mathcal{S}'_* = \mathcal{S}'_* \cup \mathcal{S}'_i$ 6: end for 7: Extract the non-dominated front \mathcal{S}'_* </pre>	<p>▷ Parallel Execution in Parallel MO-QAOA</p>
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4.1 Sequential Multi-Objective QAOA

This approach goes along with the *a priori* proposal discussed in [3]. In this sense, the QAOA's has some interesting features such as (I) its parameters' transference and (II) theoretical guarantee of optimality when p tends to ∞ . So, the core of our proposal relies on keeping the vanilla QAOA unitary transformation $\mathcal{U}_{(\gamma,\beta)}$ (see Eq. (1)) to explore the usefulness of some of the above-mentioned QAOA's features when designing our proposal.

Weighted-Sum Scalarisation We tackle a given multi-objective problem as the aggregation of its multiple objective functions $\{\mathcal{F}_1, \dots, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{K}}\}$, where $\mathcal{F}_i : x \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, and $i = 1, \dots, \mathcal{K}$. This work focuses mainly on QUBOs, although, it is applicable on higher order pseudo-Boolean problems as indicated in Section 4.3. Unlike the work done in [3], where the penalty functions are dissociated from the aggregation of the problem (see Eq. (5)), here the penalty functions are considered as part of the QUBO to be solved and, therefore, they will receive the same aggregation coefficient as the original QUBO. This is done because the penalty coefficient is tailored to have the sought impact on how to avoid feasible solutions to be penalised and unfeasible solutions to be kept. The proposed aggregation is done using Eq. (6), where x is the vector of the problem's variables, \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{P} are the upper triangular matrices of the QUBO's and penalty function coefficients, respectively, which translates to a new QUBO to be solved.

$$\mathcal{F}_* = \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i (x^T \mathcal{Q}_i x) + w_p \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x^T \mathcal{P}_j x \right), \quad w_p = 1, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_* = \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i (x^T \mathcal{Q}_i x + x^T \mathcal{P}_i x), \quad \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i = 1. \quad (6)$$

The problem defined by Eq. (6) is solved using the vanilla QAOA (see Section 2.1), and a set \mathcal{S} of solutions are sampled. A subset $\mathcal{S}' \subset \mathcal{S}$ of non-dominated solutions are extracted in $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{L}|\mathcal{S}|^2)$. Having \mathcal{Z} aggregation-weight configurations will induce repeating this process \mathcal{Z} times. The final non-dominated front \mathcal{S}'_* is extracted from the union of all \mathcal{Z} non-dominated fronts resulting by solving \mathcal{F}_* using a given weight configuration (see Eq. (7)).

$$\mathcal{S}'_* = \left\{ \mathcal{D} \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^{\mathcal{Z}} \mathcal{S}'_i \mid \forall s \in \mathcal{D}, \nexists s' \prec s, s' \in \bigcup_{i=1}^{\mathcal{Z}} \mathcal{S}'_i \right\}. \quad (7)$$

Tchebycheff Scalarisation We extend our proposal to Tchebycheff decomposition [16] since it is said to be robust when approaching peculiar fronts such as non-convex ones (see Eq. (8)). We propose both an algorithmic and mathematical implementation, which as far as our knowledge, is the first Tchebycheff implementation applicable to QAOA on quantum machines.

$$\min_x \mathcal{F}_*(x|\mathcal{W}, \mathcal{R}^*) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq \mathcal{L}} \{w_i |(x^T \mathcal{Q}_i x + x^T \mathcal{P}_i x) - r_i^*|\}, \quad \sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i = 1. \quad (8)$$

The algorithmic approach computes the **min-max** in $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{L}^2)$, where \mathcal{R}^* is the chosen reference point (see Algorithm 2). Although this approach can reproduce the **min-max** relation, if the stochastic optimisation process of γ and β is removed, it is likely to reproduce the same solution to $(x^T \mathcal{Q}_i x + x^T \mathcal{P}_i x) - r_i^*$, regardless of the aggregation weights (like in randomised algorithms using the same seed).

Algorithm 2 Tchebycheff Algorithmic Approach

Require: \mathcal{R}^* : reference point, \mathcal{Z} : aggregation-weight configurations

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1:  $\mathcal{S}'_* = \{\}$ 
2: for  $i = 1 \dots \mathcal{Z}$  do
3:    $\mathcal{T}_* = \{\}$ 
4:   for  $j = 1 \dots \mathcal{L}$  do
5:      $t_i = \text{optimise} \left( (x^T \mathcal{Q}_j x + x^T \mathcal{P}_j x) - r_j^* \right)$ 
6:      $\mathcal{T}_* = \mathcal{T}_* \cup \{t_i\}$ 
7:   end for
8:    $m_g = \infty$  and  $t_g = \{\}$ 
9:   for  $k = 1 \dots \mathcal{L}$  do
10:     $m_d = 0$  and  $t_d = \{\}$ 
11:    for  $l = 1 \dots |\mathcal{T}|$  do
12:       $f = \text{evaluate } w_{i,k} | (x^T \mathcal{Q}_k x + x^T \mathcal{P}_k x) - r_k^* |$  using  $t_l$ 
13:      if  $f > m_d$  then  $m_d = f$  and  $t_d = t_l$ 
14:    end for
15:    if  $f < m_g$  then  $m_g = m_d$  and  $t_g = t_d$ 
16:  end for
17:   $\mathcal{S}'_* = \mathcal{S}'_* \cup \{t_g\}$ 
18: end for
    
```

To cope with the drawback of the algorithmic approach, we provide a mathematical approach to the Tchebycheff scalarisation defined by Eqs. (9) and (10). For a detailed justification, one can see theorem and proof in the Appendix [5]. Knowing that $f_i(x)$ is a QUBO, one can rewrite $f_i(x) = \sum_{\mathcal{S} \subseteq [n]} \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{S}} \prod_{j \in \mathcal{S}, b \in \mathcal{E}} x_j^b = \sum_{\mathcal{S} \subseteq [n]} \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{S}} \prod_{j \in \mathcal{S}} x_j$, $x_j \in \{0, 1\}$ and \mathcal{E} is the powers' subset. It can be guaranteed that the Tchebycheff scalarisation will result in a polynomial of degree higher than 2, which can be solved by constructing the corresponding ansatz using Eq. (10) [2], where **CNOT** and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{Z}}$ are the controlled-not and \mathcal{Z} rotation gates, respectively. Although, one should note that in this work we will experimentally explore the algorithmic Tchebycheff approach considering that the present work focuses on QUBO, besides that higher-order polynomials might induce extra transpilation time and simulation resources that might jeopardize comparisons/feasibility (see Section 5.2). So, we leave the experimental assessment of the mathematical demonstration for future works especially considering our findings in Section 5.2.

$$\min_x \mathcal{F}_*(x | \mathcal{W}, \mathcal{R}^*) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{L}} w_i^p \sum_{j=0}^p \binom{p}{j} (x^T \mathcal{Q}_i x + x^T \mathcal{P}_i x)^j (-r_i^*)^{p-j} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, p = 2k, k \in \mathbb{Z}, k \rightarrow \infty \quad (9)$$

$$e^{-\gamma \bigotimes_{\mathcal{S} \subseteq [n], j \in \mathcal{S}} \mathcal{Z}_j} = \prod_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{S}|-1} \text{CNOT}_{(d_i, d_{i+1})} \mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{Z}_{|\mathcal{S}|}}(2\gamma) \prod_{i=|\mathcal{S}|-1}^1 \text{CNOT}_{(d_i, d_{i+1})}, \mathcal{S} = \{d_1, \dots, d_{\mathcal{N}}\} \quad (10)$$

QAOA Parameters’ Transference The work in [13] proved that for different instances of the MAX-Cut problem, optimal QAOA’s parameters (γ and β) can be sampled from the same distribution, and another work [14] showed that they can be transferable from one instance to another. Here, the QAOA’s parameters transference is explored in its simplest form, by passing the optimised QAOA’s parameters values when solving \mathcal{F}_* using the i^{th} weight configuration $i = 1, \dots, \mathcal{Z}$, as a seed to the optimiser when solving \mathcal{F}_* using the $(i + 1)^{th}$ weight configuration. Algorithm 1 depicts the sequential MO-QAOA workflow.

4.2 Parallel Multi-Objective QAOA

Nowadays quantum computers are in their NISQ era, so most of today’s manufacturers provide access to quantum computers for a limited time (usually upon fee), and also long queuing when executing sequential computation. Using the devised approach in [3] or the sequential version devised in this work might pose a bottleneck towards the applicability of the proposed approaches. On the other hand, the same manufacturers that provide limited time of computation, provide access to several machines. So, neglecting to some degree QAOA’s transference (Section 4.1), one can take advantage of this fact by solving in parallel, the \mathcal{Z} instances of \mathcal{F}_* on \mathcal{Z} quantum computers, and then extracting the global non-dominated front \mathcal{S}'_* on the classical machine. When using Tchebycheff scalarisation, the parallelism is applied for computing $w_i |(x^T Q_i x + x^T P_i x) - r_i^*|$ (see Pseudo-code of Algorithm 1). This approach turns out to be beneficial also when using quantum computer simulators considering the availability of several classical machines. It stands in solving \mathcal{F}_* by using a quantum computer simulator on \mathcal{Z} classical machines, where each machine will run a given weight configuration. This can overcome the bottleneck of time-limited QC and take advantage of classical computation to facilitate quantum simulation (see Figure 2). The communication between the server and quantum simulators/machines is used to dispatch the \mathcal{Z} instances of the weighted problem. So, communication complexity grows linearly $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{Z})$ considering the number of weights’ aggregations.

Fig. 2. The proposed parallel MO-QAOA

4.3 Consequences of the Proposed MO-QAOA Design

Regarding our proposal’s design, two consequences must be highlighted: (I) it can be used to solve higher-order polynomial problems. Considering the findings in [15], we expect our approach to be more efficient on higher-order polynomials. (II) the current design of our approach allows applying other decomposition methods which enables dealing with more complex Pareto fronts.

5 Experimental Results and Analysis

The implementation has been done using Python 3.10.12 and bash scripting. The execution has been done on a server using Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS 64 bits (7 CPUs and 16 GB of RAM) and a cluster with the configuration given in Table 1 using Linux Enterprise Server 15 SP4 15.4 OS. IBM Qiskit version 1.0.2 has been used for quantum execution/simulation. The QAOA has been run using COBYLA optimiser and sampled 128 times with a depth $p = \log(\mathcal{N})$ following findings in [13], where \mathcal{N} is the problem’s size. Comparisons have been made against the Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) [7] and the Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm based on Decomposition (MOEA/D) [16]. The former have been run using 100 solutions over 500 iterations (50,000 \mathcal{M} fitness evaluations) which is (on average) much larger than the solutions’ sampled by the MO-QAOA. The experiments were repeated over 32 execution and comparison metrics such as Median and the Median Absolute Deviation (MAD) have been considered. Also, null-hypothesis tests with 5% significance have been applied.

Table 1. Hardware components of the cluster used.

Nodes	CPU / GPU	RAM	InfiniBand	Localscratch
126 × SD530	56 × Intel Xeon Gold 6230R @ 2.10GHz	200GB	HDR100	950 GB
24 × Bu11 R282-Z90	128 × AMD EPYC 7H12 @ 2.6GHz	2TB	HDR200	3.5TB
168 × IBM dx360 M4	16 × Intel E5-2670 @ 2.6GHz	32GB	FDR40	400GB
4 × DGX-A100	8 × A100 Tensor Core	1TB		14 TB

The benchmarks have been generated to assess the proposal’s scalability when dealing with different complexities in terms of type and number of objectives. Problems of 2-4 objectives, where $Q_{ij}, P_{ij} \in [-1000, 1000]$, of 4-127 variables have been generated and tackled. Table 2 summarises the benchmarks features including the problems’ number, size, type and sparsity percentage (i.e. variables with no interactions). Finally, the benchmarks have been solved using 2-2000 equally-spaced aggregation-weights’ configurations. A large literature exists on weight-aggregations selection, however, this is not the focus of the present paper and left to be explored in future works. It is to be indicated also that the size of the benchmarks solved on quantum simulators has been fixed to 29 variables representing more than 536 millions combinations. Implementing the approach for 29 variables would require using/simulating 29 qubits. Knowing that the simulation requirements grows exponentially as the quantum calculation grows, increases the simulation or real execution requirements beyond the ones that are currently available. This being said, this is an effect universal to all quantum calculation and admissible knowing that the goal of our work is a proof of concept rather than an attempt to outperform state-of-the-art classical solvers.

Table 2. Benchmark problems used in the experimental evaluation.

# Objectives	Size	Type	Q	# Aggreg. Config.
2	9, 4, 16, 32, 64 127	{min, min}	{10,20} %	{2,5,11, 44, 100, 500, 1000, 2000}
3	19	{min, max}	{10,20,30} %	{2,5,11, 44, 100, 500, 1000, 2000}
4	29	{max, max}	{10,20,30,40} %	{2,5,11}

5.1 Obtained Results and Discussion

The first set of experiments has been done to assess the sequential approach, especially when using (or not) parameters’ transference, while the second set evaluates the parallel approach. The best results are bold/yellow-shaded. Figures 3 and 4 display the **Median** and **MAD** of \mathcal{F}_* during 32 executions, when solving 2 and 3-objectives problems using 2000 aggregation-weights’ configurations. It can be observed that the parameters’ transference has small impact on the solving efficiency. This turns out to be similar in problems with 2-2000 aggregations. This observation is confirmed in Figures 5 and 6, where using (or not) parameter transference yields similar approximated Pareto front for bi and three-objective problems. This encourages the use of the parallel approach of the MO-QAOA, where no parameter transference is possible. One should note that Figures 3-6 are obtained without using parameters’ transference, but have been used since they are quite representative to both scenarios; whether using or not transference.

Fig. 3. MO-QAOA with/out trans.

Fig. 4. MO-QAOA with/out trans.

Fig. 5. MO-QAOA with/out trans.

Fig. 6. MO-QAOA with/out trans.

Figures 7 and 8 display the Hypervolume (\mathbb{H}) and IGD^+ values for 3-objectives problems with regard to the number of weight-aggregations considered, where as the number of weight-aggregation configurations increases the Hypervolume/ IGD^+ value becomes better. This was expected and demonstrates the relevance of our

proposal, since the it can scale easily when the number of aggregations increases. The chosen figures are of an execution that is representative of the same conclusion for both MO-QAOA with and without parameters' transference.

Fig. 7. Seq. MO-QAOA without trans.

Fig. 8. Seq. MO-QAOA without trans.

Table 3. Median Hypervolume/IGD⁺: Seq. MO-QAOA with vs. without transf.

# W	# Obj.			2				3				4			
	Alg.	Par.	Transf.	H		IGD+		H		IGD+		H		IGD+	
				Median	MAD	Median	MAD	Median	MAD	Median	MAD	Median	MAD	Median	MAD
2	WS	Yes	97.8E+6	1.4E+6	198.4E+0	98.3E+0	10.7E+12	445.4E+9	4.9E+3	308.5E+0	1.2E+18	47.2E+15	12.5E+3	549.6E+0	
		No	97.1E+6	1.7E+6	218.5E+0	105.6E+0	10.7E+12	621.5E+9	4.9E+3	447.0E+0	1.2E+18	52.4E+15	12.6E+3	493.6E+0	
		Tcheby.	No	49.3E+6	7.9E+6	3.2E+3	866.2E+0	3.5E+12	789.6E+9	12.4E+3	1.8E+3	374.8E+15	83.5E+15	21.6E+3	2.1E+3
5	WS	Yes	99.6E+6	919.1E+3	79.9E+0	43.1E+0	12.0E+12	351.0E+9	4.2E+3	266.0E+0	1.4E+18	70.8E+15	10.9E+3	538.8E+0	
		No	99.8E+6	922.5E+3	72.1E+0	37.9E+0	12.1E+12	361.7E+9	4.0E+3	282.5E+0	1.4E+18	58.9E+15	11.2E+3	482.4E+0	
		Tcheby.	No	58.6E+6	6.4E+6	2.5E+3	467.7E+0	5.0E+12	752.0E+9	10.5E+3	1.3E+3	465.8E+15	144.5E+15	20.3E+3	2.8E+3
11	WS	Yes	100.9E+6	182.8E+3	11.6E+0	11.6E+0	13.1E+12	340.7E+9	3.3E+3	251.3E+0	1.3E+18	10.6E+15	10.1E+3	190.0E+0	
		No	100.9E+6	219.5E+3	25.1E+0	23.6E+0	13.0E+12	335.3E+9	3.4E+3	230.1E+0	1.2E+18	8.6E+15	11.3E+3	106.1E+0	
		Tcheby.	No	73.7E+6	7.6E+6	1.6E+3	459.1E+0	6.0E+12	713.0E+9	9.0E+3	3941.2E+0	646.0E+15	110.3E+15	17.6E+3	1.6E+3
SOTA	NSGA-II	Yes	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	18.9E+12	56.1E+9	404.4E+0	28.2E+0	3.0E+18	67.8E+15	3.5E+3	308.8E+0	
	MOEAD	No	100.2E+6	0.0E+0	32.9E+0	0.0E+0	10.9E+12	0.0E+0	3.8E+3	0.0E+0	1.5E+18	1.2E+15	8.7E+3	80.2E+0	

Table 4. Median Hypervolume/IGD⁺: Seq. MO-QAOA vs. SOTA

# W	# Obj.			2				3			
	Alg.	Par.	Transf.	H		IGD+		H		IGD+	
				Median	MAD	Median	MAD	Median	MAD	Median	MAD
44	WS	Yes	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	14.7E+12	277.5E+9	2.4E+3	223.1E+0	
		No	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	14.9E+12	348.6E+9	2.3E+3	117.6E+0	
100	WS	Yes	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	15.7E+12	286.2E+9	1.8E+3	120.1E+0	
		No	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	15.8E+12	342.6E+9	1.9E+3	178.5E+0	
500	WS	Yes	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	16.9E+12	326.8E+9	1.1E+3	99.1E+0	
		No	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	17.1E+12	224.8E+9	1.1E+3	127.5E+0	
1000	WS	Yes	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	17.5E+12	256.4E+9	867.7E+0	97.5E+0	
		No	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	17.4E+12	184.0E+9	894.3E+0	89.3E+0	
2000	WS	Yes	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	17.7E+12	253.7E+9	745.2E+0	91.4E+0	
		No	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	17.7E+12	211.7E+9	736.8E+0	97.1E+0	
SOTA	NSGA-II	Yes	101.1E+6	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	0.0E+0	18.9E+12	56.1E+9	404.4E+0	28.2E+0	
	MOEAD	No	100.2E+6	0.0E+0	32.9E+0	0.0E+0	10.9E+12	0.0E+0	3.8E+3	0.0E+0	

Tables 3 and 4 show the results of comparing the MO-QAOA's sequential implementation using the Weighted Sum (WS) as well Tchebycheff (Tcheby.) against the NSGA-II and MOEA/D. It can be noted that (I) as the number of aggregations increases the MO-QAOA efficiency becomes better, which is

quite expected. (II) the Tchebycheff-based MO-QAOA as well as the MOEA/D approaches are worst than the remaining solvers. This can be explained by the need of appropriate reference-point choice, which has been done *ad hoc* in this work for proof-of-concept purposes. (III) the NSGA-II is performing slightly better than the MO-QAOA. This is not alarming considering that the number of aggregations used in the MO-QAOA can grow, although it already yields very similar results to the NSGA-II. Also, many parameters such as the depth of the ansatz, the classical optimiser have a big impact on the efficiency of the proposal. On overall, we expect that increasing slightly the aggregations' number or ansatz depth will be sufficient to completely outperform the NSGA-II (see Table 4).

Table 5. Execution time in seconds: sequential vs. parallel MO-QAOA

# Obj.	# W	Sequential		Parallel Tcheby.		Time Gain (%)		Parallel WS		Time Gain (%)	
		Median	MAD	Median	MAD	%	Median	MAD	%		
2	2	5.4E+0	212.8E-3	4.8E+0	80.6E-3	11.91	3.2E+0	266.2E-3			41.32
	5	13.0E+0	415.7E-3	4.8E+0	54.2E-3	63.35	3.9E+0	651.1E-3			70.18
	11	29.6E+0	745.8E-3	5.2E+0	80.3E-3	82.47	5.3E+0	682.2E-3			82.17
3	2	50.4E+0	1.8E+0	81.9E+0	5.3E+0	-62.33	34.7E+0	927.1E-3			31.20
	5	126.8E+0	2.7E+0	83.8E+0	5.7E+0	33.93	33.5E+0	1.1E+0			73.61
	11	282.3E+0	5.4E+0	84.3E+0	1.4E+0	70.13	28.5E+0	1.4E+0			89.92
4	2	111.9E+3	3.4E+3	226.5E+3	10.4E+3	-102.41	92.5E+3	2.9E+3			17.34
	5	287.9E+3	6.1E+3	224.4E+3	3.6E+3	22.04	92.1E+3	2.1E+3			68.01
	11	507.1E+3	8.4E+3	224.9E+3	2.5E+3	55.7E+0	64.4E+3	4.9E+3			87.30

For assessing the parallel approach, we use the same experiment configurations (benchmarks, seeding, etc.), so we are not interested in the results knowing they will be similar to the sequential. Instead, we seek time reduction. So, in Table 5, it can be seen that for 2, 3, and 4-objectives problems, the execution time (in seconds) has been divided by 8 in some cases. Also, it can be noted that for each size of the problem, the time complexity remains constant, while the sequential one (similar to the literature) increases linearly in terms of the number of weight aggregations. This also applies to non-dominated front extraction, where each slave machine in the parallel approach performs a $\mathcal{O}(MN^2)$ complexity routine, while the sequential one $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{L}MN^2)$. However, one can observe that the Tchebycheff parallel implementation does not yield enhancements regarding the sequential variant. This can be explained by the $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{M}^2)$ additional comparisons and fitness evaluations to compute the min-max in Tchebycheff scalarisation.

5.2 Results on Real 127-Qubits IBM Quantum Computers

As a proof of concept, we execute our proposal on the largest real gate-based quantum computers available nowadays. We used three 127-qubits IBM quantum computers: `ibm_brisbane`, `ibm_osaka` and `ibm_kyoto` (see Figure 9). We have combined three IBM quantum-experience accounts to sum-up 30 minutes of Quantum Processing Unit (QPU) computation (IBM limits 10 minutes QPU per account). Parallel execution has been done using all accounts simultaneously where the *least-busy* machine is taken first. Still, reproducing the experiments we did on quantum simulators goes way beyond 30 minutes of real QPU. Although,

our count-based approach provides never-explored-before ideas to pass-by IBM QPU time limitations. In addition to that, since job execution of IBM quantum computers is subject to a queuing, it is not trivial to provide fair/accurate comparisons with the results obtained on quantum simulators. Indeed, following performing some experiments on April 9th, we found high sparsity in the queuing time: 1880.77" \pm 2610.53". So, the goal of this Section is to provide a proof of applicability of the proposal and eventually identify its strength/weaknesses on the current quantum computers. So, experimentation has been done only on bi-objective problems with two weight-aggregation sets on problems requiring 4, 16, 32, 64 and 127 qubits. Also, the COBYLA optimiser has been limited to only 1 iteration. The reported results are of experiments performed on 11th-16th of April 2024 at three periods of the day to draw a rough landscape of the possible queuing times: 20:00-22:00, 3:00-7:00 and 9:00-14:00.

Fig. 9. IBM QPU

Fig. 10. 64 variables

Fig. 11. 127 variables

Based on the theoretical findings in [13], p has been set to $\log(\mathcal{N})$. It can be inferred from Table 6 and [13] that the original ansatz depth follows a $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{N}\log\mathcal{N})$. However, transpilation takes increasingly larger time to produce ansatz that are increasingly more complex. This is a bottleneck considering that it will induce a larger execution time on quantum machines. As a matter of facts, the quantum computers are not available to run a $\log(\mathcal{N})$ layered ansatz for problems requiring 64 and 127 qubits, so p has been set to 1 for those benchmarks. Also, as more complex ansatz requires larger execution time, as in most classical HPC, the probability of hardware error increases with time. Indeed, in our experiments, websocket cancels after machines goes off for daily calibration/maintenance. This happened for instance at 3-5AM the 9th of April 2024. Also, the failure error increases proportionally to the ansatz's depth. When tackling problems requiring 4-32 qubits, the execution success rate is 1. It decreases to $\frac{2}{9}$, when using 64 qubits and falls to $\frac{3}{22}$ when using 127 qubits. Also, on 12th April, jobs got stuck/frozen in an endless queuing loop. In addition, to that, it can be noted the sparsity of the queuing time that spans from minutes to several hours.

Table 6 presents the Median and MAD of the original and transpiled ansatz's depth, the transpilation time, queuing time, and the overall execution time, while Figures 10-11 show the obtained non-dominated front for bi-objective problems requiring 64 and 127 qubits. It is worth noting that the queuing time considers both the sampling and expectation value estimation phases. The results in Table 6 and Figures 10-11 proves that our aggregation-based parallel MO-QAOA is

Table 6. Results on real 127-qubits IBM quantum computers

Size/Metric	Orig. Depth	Transp. Depth	Transp. Time (s)	Queuing Time (s)	Total Ex. Time (s)
4 variables	15 ± 0	603.5 ± 30.5	0.1213 ± 0.0083	106 ± 5.5	762.55
16 variables	87 ± 0	14349.5 ± 1254.5	6.4142 ± 0.0756	144 ± 26.5	655.36
32 variables	201 ± 0	48787 ± 6977.0	38.4706 ± 0.3846	3682.5 ± 4672.3	14,910.04
64 variables	129 ± 0	28384.5 ± 3205.5	32.1697 ± 0.6087	2978 ± 890.5	17,365.12
127 variables	255 ± 0	103871.5 ± 580.5	187.2764 ± 1.7365	5071.5 ± 693.0	22,678.94

feasible on real-quantum computers and optimises their use by leveraging simultaneously all the QPUs. Although, to enhance its practicality, the IBM QPU-time limitation needs to be relaxed. Also, today’s IBM transpilation would need to be enhanced to be faster and produce lighter ansatz. In addition, IBM hardware would need to be enhanced to execute more complex ansatz and calibration of machines would need to be less pervasive and avoid cancelling users’ jobs. So, to enhance our proposal’s practicality on today’s quantum computers, we plan as next step to: (I) design an ansatz that combines and optimises all the sub-problems simultaneously. (II) Design proposals that can perform well with a reduced layering to produce lighter transpiled ansatz.

6 Conclusions and Research Perspectives

This work proposes a sequential and a parallel multi-objective QAOA using weighted-sum and Tchebycheff decomposition. The experiments have been done using diverse 2-4 objectives benchmarks of different types and sparsity. Experiments have been made using 2-2000 weight-aggregation configurations running on 2000 slave machines/jobs where an IBM quantum computer simulator as well as three 127-qubits’ real quantum computers have been used. The results have shown a decrease up to 89% of the execution time, which is more suitable for today’s NISQ quantum machines, as well as taking advantage of the existing classical machines’ facilities to optimise quantum simulation. Our proposal turns out to be feasible on real quantum computers, but would be more practical if manufacturers remove QPU time limitations. This being said, as a next step, we plan to (I) implement our mathematical Tchebycheff approach, (II) test our approach on higher-order polynomials, and (III) design an approach that will combine all the problems’ objectives into one shallow quantum ansatz.

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